

THROUGHPUT ANALYSIS OF A DS-CDMA SYSTEM IN A MULTIPATH FADING CHANNEL

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results concerning the number of simultaneous users supportable by an asynchronous direct sequence code division multiple access (DS-CDMA) system using wideband noncoherent MFSK in a multipath fading channel. The result is compared to that of a DS-CDMA system using DPSK modulation obtained by Turin.

INTRODUCTION

DS-CDMA is attractive for mobile radio communication as well as satellite communication using very small aperture terminals (VSAT). In DS-CDMA, each user transmits a specific pseudo-noise (PN) code which either identifies the user to a central station of a star network or addresses another user in a mesh network. The user's PN codes are selected from a set of quasi-orthogonal codes such as Gold codes or Kasami codes that have good autocorrelation functions and low crosscorrelation functions so that the multi-user noise or crosscorrelation noise is kept small. This allows a large number of users to access the channel simultaneously while the system performance, that is, the bit error rate degrades gracefully as the number of simultaneous users increases. Furthermore, each user may transmit asynchronously and no time or frequency scheduling of the channel is required.

The DS-CDMA system considered here employs noncoherent MFSK to modulate the information signal at bit rate R_b into MFSK signal at the symbol rate $R_s = R_b / \log_2 M$. The spectrum of the MFSK signal is then spread over the channel bandwidth by multiplying it with a PN code at chip rate $R_c = RR_s$ where R is the PN code length. In a conventional MFSK modulation scheme, the frequency spacing is the symbol rate. This frequency spacing minimizes the total signal bandwidth while maintaining the orthogonality between symbols. Minimizing

the signal bandwidth is of no concern here since we intend to spread the signal bandwidth anyway. The modulation is generalized to allow frequency spacing between MFSK symbols of $\Delta = nR_s$ (n is an integer and $n > 1$). It is shown that using $n > 1$ increases the multiple access considerably by whitening the multi-user interference power spectral density at the receiver. Since n is integer, the symbols are still orthogonal and noncoherent demodulation is still possible. The bit error probability as a function of the number of interfering users is determined assuming the multi-user interference is Gaussian but colored.

SYSTEM MODELING

We assume that each user is assigned a distinct PN code selected from a set of quasi-orthogonal codes such as Gold codes or Kasami codes [1-3]. The multiple access mode is asynchronous, that is, no attempt is made to align the code period of various users at the receiver. The performance analysis is based on the assumption that the effect of multi-user interference is equivalent to adding more Gaussian noise to the channel. For this assumption to hold, the number of interfering users N should be reasonably small compared to the number of chips per symbol or code length R , that is, $N/R \gg 1$. Increasing N while keeping R constant produces the same interference effect as decreasing R while keeping N constant, and a small R implies that the despread bandwidth of the interfering signals at the receiver would be narrower than when R is larger. The statistics of an arbitrary signal passed through the receiver filter with a bandwidth much narrower than the despread bandwidth approach a Gaussian distribution according to the central limit theorem and the related Berry-Essen theorem [4]. Therefore, the multi-user interference of a system using a larger R for a fixed N (or equivalently, a smaller N for a fixed R) would be more Gaussian than that of a system with a smaller R for the same N (or equivalently, a larger N for the same R) at the output of a receiver.

If the PN code is long, it can be approximated by a random signature code of independent chips, each

of which takes values 1 or -1 with equal probability 1/2. The random signature codes for different users are assumed to be statistically independent. The autocorrelation of a random signature code with chip duration T is

$$p(\tau) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{|\tau|}{T} = 1 - \frac{R|\tau|}{T_s} & |\tau| \leq T = T_s/R \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

There has been a large volume of information published about multipath fading. When it is taken into account in the analysis of a particular communications system multipath fading is usually assumed to be a Rayleigh faded path. This assumption is an approximation of a real multipath faded channel. In the following analysis we do not rely on Rayleigh distribution which characterizes a multipath faded channel. Instead, the analysis relies heavily on an experiment performed by Turin, Hashemi and Kamil [5-8]. This experiment involved fixing a transmitter at an elevated site in the San Francisco area. Once per second a 100-ns pulse was transmitted and then received in a van driving through designated sections of the city. The collected data was then analyzed to determine its statistical properties. A computer program was developed, called SURP (Simulation of Urban Radio Propagation), that would generate multipath delay profiles exhibiting the statistical properties of real urban/suburban multipath fading. Figure 1 shows a sample multipath delay profile. Each vertical line represents a delay signal with signal strength (dB) and time delay (μs) shown. It is this type of data that is used to characterize the multipath effects on the DS-CDMA system.

The channel noise consists of the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) the self-noise which is formed by interference signals generated from the desired signal by the multipath fading effect, and the multiuser interference that has undergone multipath fading. Assume that the symbol at frequency f_p is transmitted, then the total received signal at the zeroth receiver can be expressed by

$$r(t) = s_0(t) + n_s(t) + n_u(t) + n_{ih}(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T_s \quad (2)$$

where $s_0(t)$ is the desired signal for symbol " f_p " at the zeroth receiver, $n_s(t)$ is the self-noise, $n_u(t)$ represents the multiuser interference, and $n_{ih}(t)$ is the AWGN with a zero mean and power spectral density $N_0/2$. The components of $r(t)$ in (2) are given by

$$s_0(t) = a_{0x} p_0(t) \cos(2\pi f_p t + \theta_0), \quad 1 \leq x \leq L \quad (3)$$

$$n_s(t) = \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq x}}^L a_{0i} p_0(t - \tau_{0i}) \cos(2\pi f_p t + \theta_{0i}) \quad (4)$$

$$n_u(t) = \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{i=N_{k-1}+1}^{N_k} a_{il} p_i(t - \tau_{il}) \cos(2\pi f_k t + \theta_{il}) \quad (5)$$

where L is the total number of delayed path presented to the zeroth receiver, and

a_{0x} : random variable representing the signal strength of the desired signal at the zeroth receiver associated with the x th path.

a_{0l} : random variable representing the signal strength of the desired signal at the zeroth receiver associated with the l th faded path.

a_{il} : random variable representing the signal strength of the i th CDMA signal at the zeroth receiver associated with the l th faded path.

$p_i(t)$: random signature code of the i th CDMA signal.

τ_{0l} : time delay of the desired signal associated with the l th faded path relative to the x th faded path.

τ_{il} : time delay of the i th CDMA signal associated with the l th faded path relative to the desired signal associated with the x th faded path.

$\theta_{0l} = \theta_i + 2\pi f_k \tau_{il}$ where θ_i is the phase of the transmitted i th CDMA signal.

$k \lfloor N/M \rfloor \leq N_k \leq k \lfloor N/M \rfloor + k$, $\lfloor Z \rfloor =$ integer part of Z
 $\sum_{k=1}^M (N_k - N_{k-1}) = N$

$E\{N_k - N_{k-1}\} = N/M$ where $E\{\cdot\}$ is the expected value.

We assume that all relative time delays are smaller than the symbol duration T_s , hence the intersymbol interference effect is negligible. Also we assume that all paths created by the multipath effect can be resolved, that is, one path can be separated in time from earlier and later paths. This amounts to requiring $|\tau_{0l}| \geq T$ where T is the chip rate. The resolvability can be met with a bandwidth in the order of 10 MHz or more.

ANALYSIS

An MFSK/DS-CDMA modulator transmitting M distinct symbols s_1, s_2, \dots, s_M is shown in Figure 2. A noncoherent demodulator consists of M parallel channels (Figure 3), each channel has two correlators and two squarers. The sampled outputs of these channels define a set of observables r_m , $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$, which are related to the observables r_{mc} and r_{ms} by

$$r_m = (r_{mc}^2 + r_{ms}^2)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

Note that r_m 's are independent observables due to the orthogonal frequency spacing. Let s_p denote the transmitted MFSK symbol at frequency f_p . The symbol error probability given s_p was transmitted is

$$\begin{aligned}
P_e(s_p) &= 1 - Pr\left\{\bigcap_{\substack{q=1 \\ q \neq p}}^M (r_q < r_p \mid s_p)\right\} \\
&= 1 - \int_0^\infty \int_0^{r_p} \cdots \int_0^{r_p} \prod_{q=1}^M p(r_q \mid s_p) dr_1 dr_2 \cdots dr_M
\end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here $p(r_q \mid s_p)$ is the probability density function of the observable r_q given s_p was transmitted and can be expressed by

$$p(r_p \mid s_p) = \frac{r_p}{\sigma_p^2} \exp\left(-\frac{r_p^2 + E_s^2}{2\sigma_p^2}\right) I_0\left(\frac{E_s r_p}{\sigma_p^2}\right), \quad q = p \quad (8)$$

$$p(r_q \mid s_p) = \frac{r_q}{\sigma_q^2} \exp\left(-\frac{r_q^2}{2\sigma_q^2}\right), \quad q \neq p \quad (9)$$

where

$I_0(\cdot)$: modified Bessel function of first kind and order zero

$E_s = E\{a_{0x}^2\}T_s/2$: MFSK symbol energy of the desired signal associated with the x th faded path

σ_p^2 : variance of the observable r_{pc} (or r_{ps}) which is the power of AWGN plus self-noise and multiuser interference at the output of the correlators in channel p .

σ_q^2 : variance of the observable r_{qc} (or r_{qs}) which is the power of AWGN plus multiuser interference at the output of the correlators in channel q .

Substituting (8) and (9) into (7) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
P_e(s_p) &= 1 - \int_0^\infty \frac{r_p}{\sigma_p^2} \exp\left(-\frac{r_p^2 + E_s^2}{2\sigma_p^2}\right) I_0\left(\frac{E_s r_p}{\sigma_p^2}\right) \\
&\quad \times \prod_{\substack{q=1 \\ q \neq p}}^M \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{r_q^2}{2\sigma_q^2}\right)\right] dr_p
\end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Because the interference is not white but colored, the symbol error probability is symbol dependent. The average symbol error probability is found by averaging over all of the symbols

$$P_e = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{p=1}^M P_e(s_p) \quad (11)$$

The average bit error probability can be approximated by the relation

$$P_b = \frac{M/2}{M-1} P_e \quad (12)$$

It remains to determine $\sigma_p^2, p = 1, 2, \dots, M$ so that (10)–(12) can be evaluated. Note that

$$r_{pc} = \int_0^{T_s} p_0(t)r(t) \cos(2\pi f_p t) dt \quad (13)$$

where $r(t)$ is given by (2)–(5). Expanding (13) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
r_{pc} &= \frac{1}{2} T_s a_{0x} \cos \theta_0 \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{l=1 \\ l \neq p}}^L a_{0l} \cos \theta_{0l} \int_0^{T_s} p_0(t - \tau_{0l}) p_0(t) dt \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{i=N_{k-1}-1}^{N_k} a_{il} \cos \theta_{il} \\
&\quad \times \int_0^{T_s} p_i(t - \tau_{il}) p_0(t) \cos [2\pi \Delta(k-p)t] dt \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{i=N_{k-1}-1}^{N_k} a_{il} \sin \theta_{il} \\
&\quad \times \int_0^{T_s} p_i(t - \tau_{il}) p_0(t) \cos [2\pi \Delta(k-p)t] dt \\
&\quad + \int_0^{T_s} n(t) p_0(t) \cos(2\pi f_p t) dt
\end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta = n/T_s, n = 1, 2, \dots$ is the orthogonal frequency spacing between MFSK symbols and

$$\Delta(k-p) = f_k - f_p \quad (15)$$

Similarly, the observable $r_{qc}, q \neq p$ is given by (14) without the first term on the right side and with p replaced by q .

In the determination of $\sigma_p^2, p = 1, 2, \dots, M$ one needs to calculate the following quantity:

$$\begin{aligned}
Z &= \int_0^{T_s} \int_0^{T_s} E\{p_i(t_1 - \tau_{il}) p_i(t_2 - \tau_{il})\} E\{p_0(t_1) p_0(t_2)\} \\
&\quad \times \cos [2\pi \Delta(k-p)t_1] \cos [2\pi \Delta(k-p)t_2] dt_1 dt_2 \\
&= \int_0^{T_s} \int_0^{T_s} \frac{1}{2} p^2(t_1 - t_2) \{ \cos [2\pi \Delta(k-p)(t_1 - t_2)] \\
&\quad + \cos [2\pi \Delta(k-p)(t_1 + t_2)] \} dt_1 dt_2
\end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

After changing variables $\tau = t_1 - t_2, \alpha = t_1 + t_2$ and knowing that the determinant of the Jacobian matrix

equals 2, it can be shown that (16) reduces to

$$Z = \int_0^{T_s} \int_{\tau}^{2T_s - \tau} \frac{1}{2} p^2(\tau) \left\{ \cos [2\pi\Delta(k-p)\tau] + \cos [2\pi\Delta(k-p)\alpha] \right\} d\alpha d\tau$$

where $p(\tau)$ is given in (1). After some algebraic manipulation we arrive at the following result

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_p^2 &= \frac{N_0 T_s}{4} + \frac{T_s^2}{4} \left(\frac{1}{3R} - \frac{1}{12R^2} \right) \sum_{i=1}^L E\{a_{0i}^2\} \\ &+ \frac{T_s^2}{2} \cdot \frac{N}{M} \left(\frac{1}{3R} - \frac{1}{12R^2} \right) \sum_{i=1}^L E\{a_{ii}^2\} \\ &+ \frac{T_s^2}{4} \cdot \frac{N}{M} \sum_{k=2}^M \sum_{l=1}^L E\{a_{il}^2\} \frac{R}{2\pi n(k-p)} \\ &\times \left\{ 2 + \frac{1}{R} + \frac{10R \cos [2\pi n(k-p)/R] - 10R}{[2\pi n(k-p)]^2} \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{2(1-R) \sin [2\pi n(k-p)/R]}{2\pi n(k-p)} \right\} \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

where for a given frequency spacing Δ , $n = T_s \Delta$.

Similarly σ_q^2 , $q \neq p$ is given by (17) without the first term on the right side and with p replaced by q .

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The multipath delay profiles are used to provide the data necessary for the system simulation. These delay profiles characterize the multipath fading characteristics in four different environments, namely: Area A, heavily built-up urban area; Area B, downtown part of a city; Area C, downtown part of a small size city; and Area D, residential suburbs of cities. The data used for simulation in this paper was the data generated by SURP assuming operation in Area A. Figure 4 shows the bit error probability versus the average bit energy-to-noise density ratio for MFSK/DS-CDMA in Area A for $N = 16$ interfering users. There is an average $L = 15$ faded paths for each of the $N + 1 = 17$ users in the channel. The parameters are: $M = 16$, $n = 256$, $R = 1023$, $R_b = 6$ kbps and bandwidth $B = 8.83$ MHz. Figure 5 shows the performance for the same number of users with $M = 32$, $n = 256$, $R = 1023$, $R_b = 6$ kbps and $B = 12$ MHz. With DPSK, the number of users for the same bit rate and spread bandwidth is about eight times smaller [6]. The number of users can be increased manifold by diversity combining and error correction coding.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 5

Figure 4